

Issue with the Maxwell-Boltzmann Tail?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 11, 2020

In this note, we attempt to examine the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) equilibrium distribution tail i.e. $\exp(-e/T)$ for $e \gg T$. We first consider counting arguments presented in (1) to obtain the Bose-Einstein distribution and its limit of high T to learn about the tail. Secondly, we consider the balance equation $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ which follows from the Boltzmann transport equation (or an "and" probability scheme) for the elastic reaction $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and try to argue that the MB tail may not actually occur.

Counting Scheme for the Bose Einstein Distribution

In (1), the following picture is presented. Imagine there are energy levels e_i . In equilibrium, each will contain an average number of particles n_i , where n_i is taken to be a large number so that Stirling's approximation may be applied. This is important because the calculation of the Bose Einstein form depends directly on the Stirling approximation. In addition, assume (it is not sure why) that each e_i level contains g_i cells (each with the same energy). It seems the only restriction on g_i is that it must be greater than 1. If there are g_i cells, there exist g_i-1 inner partitions or walls, if one assumes a "wall" exists at each end. Thus, the number of ways of arranging n_i identical particles in such a system is given by:

$$\text{Number of states} = \text{Product over } i \quad (n_i+g_i-1)! / [n_i! (g_i-1)!] \quad ((1))$$

If $g_i=1$, one has $(n_i+g_i-1)! / [n_i! (g_i-1)!] = 1/(g_i-1)!$ which cannot be varied with respect to n . Any other g_i is acceptable it seems. In a previous note, we argued that this scheme seems to be the same for bosons or for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. There does not seem to be any physical argument to distinguish between the two.

The approach of (1) is to vary: $-\ln(\text{Number of States}) + b \sum_i e_i n_i$ where b is a Lagrange multiplier. If n_i is large, one may apply Stirling's approximation to both factorials including n_i regardless of the value of g_i . Thus one maximizes:

$$(n_i+g_i-1) \ln[n_i+g_i-1] - n \ln(n) + b n_i (e_i-u) \quad ((2)) \quad (u = \text{the chemical potential}) \quad \text{or}$$

$$\ln[(n_i+g_i-1)/n_i] = -b n_i e_i \quad \text{or} \quad n_i = (1-g_i) / [1 - \exp(b(e_i-u))] \quad \text{the Bose Einstein distribution} \quad ((3))$$

It is usually assumed that g_i is much greater than 1 so that $1-g_i$ becomes $-g_i$.

We wish to examine this approach in more detail. Given that the only restriction on g_i is that it be greater than 1, consider $g_i=2$. Then from ((1))

$$(n_i+1)! / [n_i! (g_i-1)!] = (n_i+1) / (g_i-1)!$$

Thus, one maximizes $-\ln(n_i+1) + b(e_i-u)n_i$ to obtain: $1/[b(e_i-u)] - 1 = n_i$ ((4))

The original argument, however, requires that $n_i \gg 1$ so b must approach zero without e_i interfering. b is usually taken to be $1/T$ so this means $1/T \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e. becomes large). The problem with this approach is that it creates a problem with the tail because e_i can always be greater than T .

Thus, it seems that the "tail" behaviour may not be reliable.

An immediate question which arises is how are ((4)) and ((3)) related?

$n_i = (1-g_i) / [1 - \exp(b(e_i-u))] = -1 / [1 - 1 - b(e_i-u) + \dots] = 1/[b(e_i-u)]$ which is the same as ((4))

If one drops the 1 on the LHS which is fine because $n_i \gg 1$. Note: $b=1/T$ so n_i goes as T .

Thus, the tail of the Bose-Einstein distribution for T becoming large may not be reliable, but this is the Maxwell-Boltzmann tail according to arguments presented in textbooks regarding the large T limit of the Bose-Einstein distribution.

Reaction Approach

An equilibrium solution to the Boltzmann transport equation is:

$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ ((5)) This may also be considered as an "and" probability condition with

time reversal balance for the elastic reaction $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. Thus, if one takes \ln of ((5)) one obtains a conservation equation which may be linked to energy or $-1/T(e_i-u)$ where u is the chemical potential (the fugacity becoming a normalization constant), namely:

$\ln(f(e_i)) = -1/T(e_i-u)$ ((6)) which yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

Everything seems to be in balance. For every e_1 and e_2 which convert into e_3 and e_4 , there is an e_3 and e_4 converting into e_1 and e_2 , hence equilibrium. We suggest, however, there may be a problem with this picture for the tail, i.e. for e_i much larger than T . First, of all there is the issue with a cutoff which does not naturally appear in this approach. e_i cannot physically go to infinite, although it is taken to do so because the MB distribution drops quickly enough. More importantly, however, seems to be the following concern. Imagine e_i states which are much larger than T . In such a case, $f(e_i)$ is very small. The reaction balance seems to be based on the idea that in a small time Δt , both forward and time reversed reactions occur maintaining a balance in $f(e_i)$ numbers in a local region. A problem, it seems, would arise if $f(e_i)$ is so small that one cannot guarantee that if a forward reaction occurs in Δt , its time reverse also occurs in the same time frame. For very low $f(e_i)$ probabilities, the reverse reaction may occur some time later. Thus, the system is pushed slightly off equilibrium when a reaction containing an e_i such that $f(e_i)$ is very low occurs i.e. a reaction with a very high energy particle. This

particle may impart locally quite a bit of energy by crashing into other particles, or might draw out quite a bit of energy if it gets “created” through collision. The system would then try to re-establish “equilibrium” which might occur before the time reversed reaction occurs. Thus, we suggest the time scale for reaction-time reversed reactions is important. If they do not both occur in the same Δt in a relatively small region, equilibrium is disrupted. It seems that even though there may be global equilibrium, the idea of equilibrium balance also applies locally. Thus, we argue that the tail of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may not be accurate.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to present two arguments related to possible issues with the Maxwell-Boltzmann equilibrium tail. The first is related to a Boltzmann entropy calculation of the Bose Einstein distribution using factorials. It suggests that the calculation only holds for e_i values smaller than T , i.e. not for the tail for $1/T$ approaching zero i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann region. For the second argument, we consider $f(e_i)$ being so small that reactions and time reversed reactions cannot occur locally in the same Δt period. Thus, locally it would seem that equilibrium is being disrupted by these high e_i reactions and so the Maxwell-Boltzmann tail's mathematical form $\exp(-1/T(e_i-u))$ for $e_i \gg T$ which depends on a reaction balance may be suspect. In other words, the expression $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ used to obtain the MB distribution may not really hold if $f(e_i)$ is very small because there is no local balance in a Δt time frame in such a case.

References

1. Huang, Kerson. Statistical Physics. Wiley 1987. Page 182